

Reusable and inductively regenerable magnetic activated carbon for removal of organic micropollutants from secondary wastewater effluents

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INTRODUCTION

Powdered activated carbon (PAC) is one of the most suitable adsorbents for organic micropollutants (such as pharmaceuticals, personal care products, steroid hormones, pesticides, industrial chemicals and numerous other emerging contaminants) with many operational full-scale plants across Germany and Switzerland. Nevertheless, one of the major challenges with PAC is the difficult solid-liquid separation and short life cycle which requires disposal and/or incineration of the micropollutants-loaded spent PAC after reaching its full adsorption capacity.

Moreover, the cost of raw materials, particularly for lignite-based and especially for coconut shell-based charcoal, has surged in the last few years as a result of the rapidly rising global industrial demand for activated carbon, the higher energy prices for its production, disrupted supply chains due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the scarcity of high-grade coal, reducing the production capacity of the manufacturers. Consequently, PAC producers are focusing more efforts on reactivating and reusing spent PAC, however, the classical thermal reactivation has a high carbon footprint. Thus, there is a research demand for a more environmentally friendly and cost-efficient method for PAC regeneration, which will provide a more sustainable and economically viable adsorbent for micropollutants removal from secondary WWTP effluents.

This research work is a proof-of-concept for the synthesis and application of a magnetically harvestable, regenerable and reusable magnetic powdered activated carbon (mPAC), which will eliminate the need for large sedimentation tanks and flocculants required for the implementation of classical PAC and make the adsorptive removal of micropollutants from wastewater more sustainable [1].

METHODS

This work introduces the synthesis of engineered magnetic powdered activated carbon (mPAC) designed for quick and efficient inductive regeneration and long-term reuse of the proposed novel adsorbent. In concept (see Fig.1), the mPAC is first used for micropollutants adsorption, then magnetically harvested from the wastewater stream, thermally regenerated in a low energy consuming inductive heating device (Fig.2), and finally reused in a new adsorption cycle:

Figure 1 – Schematic of an adsorption-regeneration-wash-reuse cycle of magnetic powdered activated carbon (mPAC) for the removal of organic micropollutants (OMPs) from secondary wastewater effluents. Reference: [1]

The mPAC synthesis was performed with modifications based on already published procedures by combining commercial activated carbons with magnetic iron oxide (e.g. Fe_3O_4) nanoparticles, adapting two different synthesis approaches for iron oxide integration:

- Infiltration method (“infiltr”) after Schwickardi et al. [2] and
- Surface deposition method (“depos”) after Oliveira et al. [3].

The two different magnetization methods were compared after applying them on two different commercial PACs provided by the company Jacobi Carbons GmbH:

- Lignite-based PAC (“L”) Aquasorb MP25 (1187 m^2/g) and
- Coconut-based PAC (“C”) Addisorb GA (1524 m^2/g).

Figure 2 – Bench-scale magnetic induction device Sinus-52 from Himmelwerk GmbH (left) and coupled double-loop round copper coil (right) used to inductively regenerate the mPACs.

Intensive preliminary comparison tests (kinetics, isotherms, optimization of mPAC regeneration, etc.) were performed with all mPACs. One specific mPAC was recommended for further detailed experiments. Then optimal conditions were found for the application and reuse of the magnetic carbons in a real municipal wastewater effluent (WWTP Uni Stuttgart), and the removal efficiency of a broad range of specific organic micropollutants was tested with the best performing mPAC under optimal conditions over 5 adsorption-regeneration-reuse cycles.

CONCLUSIONS

- Two commercial powdered activated carbons (PAC), lignite “L” and coconut “C”-based, were successfully equipped with magnetic properties via deposition (“depos”) or infiltration (“infiltr”) of iron oxide nanoparticles (21–31 wt%).
- This made the PACs magnetically separable (saturation magnetization 16 emu/g) and inductively heatable (maximum temp. 675°C reached within 10 s) to facilitate easy magnetic solid-liquid separation, inductive regeneration and efficient long-term reuse of the mPACs.
- Experiments with secondary effluent wastewater revealed fast adsorption of the organic load on the mPACs (following the pseudo-2nd-order kinetic and Freundlich isotherm models) with insignificant deviations in adsorption capacity compared to their virgin precursor PACs.
- During inductive regeneration, the infiltrated mPACs outperformed the ones of the deposition synthesis route, with sample “L-infiltr” having the best overall performance.
- In cyclical reuse tests, “L-infiltr” showed ~3% drop in organics removal efficiency per regeneration cycle compared to ~10% drop per cycle without inductive regeneration.
- Additional analysis of 31 specific organic micropollutants (OMPs) showed that for 28 OMPs adsorption efficiency was consistently high (> 75%) and dropped by < 5% after 5 cycles.
- The mPAC “L-infiltr” has a potential to be a superior alternative to existing commercial PACs.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Table 1 – Comparing the physico-chemical characteristics of all as-synthesized mPACs against their non-magnetic PAC precursors (lignite “L” and coconut “C”), incl. before and after induction heating (IH) of the mPACs.

Sample Name	Carbon Content (wt%)	Iron Content (wt%)	BET Surface Area before IH (m^2/g)	BET Surface Area after IH (m^2/g)	Total Pore Volume before IH (cm^3/g)	Total Pore Volume after IH (cm^3/g)	Micropore Volume (cm^3/g)	Microporosity (%)
L	100	0	1187	-	0.78	-	0.32	42
L-infiltr	69	31	948	876	0.58	0.56	0.08	14
L-depos	69	31	896	887	0.60	0.58	0.11	18
C	100	0	1524	-	0.69	-	0.59	86
C-infiltr	77	23	1187	1156	0.54	0.58	0.20	37
C-depos	79	21	1062	1107	0.51	0.53	0.22	43

Figure 3 – Magnetization curves (left) and induction heating curves (right) of all as-synthesized mPACs.

Remark: Induction heating was run for 60 s at 1521 Hz applied frequency. The plotted average values (n=2) show maximum temperature 675°C reached in only 10 s for the mPAC “L-infiltr”. Reference: [1]

Figure 4 – Effect of inductive regeneration: SAC_{254} removal for magnetic carbons “L-infiltr” (150 mg/L) and “C-infiltr” (200 mg/L) throughout 5 cycles of reuse with (solid lines, grey squares/circles) and without (dotted lines, empty squares/circles) intermediate “wet inductive” regeneration, compared with simple drying at 50°C (black “X”). Adsorption: pH 7, 22°C, 20 min. The plotted values are average of two repetitions (n=2) with max ±5% deviation. Reference: [1]

Figure 5 – Visualization of material stability and magnetic separation with 1.3 T hand magnet (NdFeB) for all as-synthesized magnetic carbons (mPACs) at pH 2, 7, 13. Remark: 50 mg mPAC in 15 mL water, stirred at 700 rpm for 90 min, followed by 30 s magnetic separation. Reference: [1]

Figure 7 – Removal of selected organic micropollutants (OMPs) and their transformation products from a secondary clarifier effluent over 5 cycles of intermediate inductive regeneration and reuse of the mPAC “L-infiltr” [1].

Figure 6 – SEM micrographs of “L-infiltr”: magnetically modified lignite with iron oxide nanoparticles (the white crystal formations in c2) via the infiltration method.

- Each cycle in Fig.7 consisted of the following main treatment steps:
- 1) **OMP adsorption phase:** 150 mg/L mPAC dose, 1 L volume pH 7, ~22°C, 20 min contact time
 - 2) **mPAC regeneration phase:** 75% power output (3.7 kW) 2 min induction exposure time
 - 3) **mPAC washing phase:** 50 mg/L NaCl saline solution 5 min stirring

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Abstract: This work proposes a new sustainable alternative of powdered activated carbon (PAC) - magnetically harvestable and reusable after regeneration via inductive heating – for the adsorptive removal of organic micropollutants (OMPs) from secondary wastewater effluents. Two commercial PACs (lignite and coconut) were modified with iron oxide via infiltration and surface deposition. Iron oxide adds beneficial magnetic properties for easy separation of the magnetic PAC (mPAC) and acts as an inductively heatable agent for the carbon regeneration. Tests with real wastewater showed fast adsorption kinetics, where the infiltrated lignite mPAC had the best performance over 5 reuse cycles with intermediate inductive regeneration (< 3% drop in organics removal per cycle with regeneration vs. ~10% drop per cycle without regeneration). The treated effluent was analysed for 31 representative OMPs (pharmaceuticals, personal care products, industrial chemicals, etc.), showing consistently high OMP removal (> 80%) and < 5% drop in efficiency after 5 cycles with intermediate regeneration.

Keywords: Magnetic induction; Organic micropollutants; Reusable powdered activated carbon

Powdered activated carbon (PAC) is one of the most suitable adsorbents for organic micropollutants (such as pharmaceuticals, personal care products, steroid hormones, pesticides, industrial chemicals and numerous other emerging contaminants) with many operational full-scale plants across Germany and Switzerland. Nevertheless, one of the major challenges with PAC is the difficult solid-liquid separation and short life cycle which requires disposal and/or incineration of the micropollutants-loaded spent PAC after reaching its full adsorption capacity. Moreover, the cost of raw materials, particularly for lignite-based and especially for coconut shell-based charcoal, has surged in the last few years as a result of the rapidly rising global industrial demand for activated carbon, the higher energy prices for its production, disrupted supply chains due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the scarcity of high-grade coal, reducing the production capacity of the manufacturers (MMR Maximize Market Research PVT. Ltd., 2022). Consequently, PAC producers are focusing more efforts on reactivating and reusing spent PAC, however, the classical thermal

reactivation has a high carbon footprint. Thus, there is a research demand for a more environmentally friendly and cost-efficient method for PAC regeneration, which will provide a more sustainable and economically viable adsorbent for micropollutants removal from secondary WWTP effluents.

This research work is a proof-of-concept for the synthesis and application of a magnetically harvestable, regenerable and reusable powdered activated carbon, which will eliminate the need for large sedimentation tanks and flocculants required for the implementation of classical PAC, and make the adsorptive removal of micropollutants from wastewater more sustainable. We introduce the synthesis of engineered magnetic powdered activated carbon (mPAC) designed for quick and efficient inductive regeneration and long-term reuse of the proposed novel adsorbent. In concept, the mPAC is first used for micropollutants adsorption, then magnetically harvested from the wastewater stream, thermally regenerated through low-energy-consuming inductive heating, and finally reused in a new adsorption cycle, as depicted in Fig. 1.1.

Figure 1.1 Schematic of an adsorption-regeneration-wash-reuse cycle of magnetic powdered activated carbon (mPAC) for the removal of organic micropollutants (OMPs) from wastewater (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2024).

The mPAC synthesis was performed with modifications based on already published procedures by combining commercial activated carbons with magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles, adapting two methods proposed by Schwickardi et al. (Schwickardi et al., 2006) and Oliveira et al. (Oliveira et al., 2002), respectively. The two different magnetization methods were compared after applying them on two different commercial PACs (lignite-based and coconut-based). One specific magnetization route was recommended for detailed testing in real wastewater. Furthermore, one of the main research questions was to find the optimal conditions for the application and reuse of the magnetic carbons in a real municipal wastewater effluent, and to analyse the removal efficiency of a broad range of specific organic

micropollutants with the best performing mPAC under optimal conditions, as shown in Fig. 1.2 below.

Figure 1.2 Removal of selected organic micropollutants (OMP) and their transformation products from a secondary clarifier effluent within 5 cycles of intermediate inductive regeneration and reuse of the magnetic mPAC “L-infiltr”. Adsorption was performed at 150 mg/L mPAC dose, pH 7, ~22°C and 20 min contact time.

The two different types of powdered activated carbon (PAC), lignite “L” (1187 m²/g) and coconut “C”-based (1524 m²/g), were successfully equipped with magnetic properties via deposition (“depos”) or infiltration (“infiltr”) of iron oxide. The modification with iron oxide (21-31 wt%) reduced the pore volume and active

surface area of the PACs by ~20-30%, but made them magnetically separable (saturation magnetization up to 16 emu/g) and inductively heatable (maximum temperature up to 675°C reached in 10 s) to facilitate easy magnetic solid-liquid separation, inductive regeneration and efficient reuse of the mPAC.

Experiments with secondary effluent wastewater revealed fast adsorption of the organic load driven by chemisorption and a multilayer adsorption process. The infiltrated mPACs, “L-infiltr” (948 m²/g) and “C-infiltr” (1187 m²/g), showed promising results with insignificant deviations in adsorption capacity compared to their precursor PACs, despite the reduced surface area. During inductive regeneration, the infiltrated mPACs outperformed the ones of the deposition synthesis route, with sample “L-infiltr” having the best overall performance. The organics-loaded mPAC “L-infiltr” preserved ~92% of its original adsorption capacity after drying and intermediate inductive regeneration, compared to only ~65% without drying and regeneration. Furthermore, the reusability of “L-infiltr” was demonstrated throughout 5 consecutive adsorption cycles with and without intermediate inductive regeneration. On average, “L-infiltr” showed ~3% drop in organics removal efficiency per regeneration cycle compared to ~10% drop per cycle without inductive regeneration (measured using sum the parameter SAC₂₅₄). This was cross-checked with additional analysis of 31 specific organic micropollutants (OMP) and their transformation products, incl. pharmaceuticals, personal care products and industrial chemicals, where for 28 OMPs adsorption efficiency was consistently high (>80%) and dropped by <5% after the 5 cycles, as shown in Fig. 1.2.

Although the process requires further optimization and upscaling, the mPAC “L-infiltr” has demonstrated its potential as a superior alternative to existing commercial PACs due to its ability to be regenerated and reused, and the possibility for magnetic harvesting which obviates the need to invest in large flocculation and sedimentation tanks.

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